

SOCIAL ISOLATION, LONELINESS, AND PHYSICAL HEALTH OUTCOMES AMONG SENIOR CITIZENS LIVING IN A GEOGRAPHICALLY ISOLATED DISADVANTAGED AREA (GIDA) COMMUNITY

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the social isolation, loneliness, and physical health outcomes among senior citizens residing in a Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Area (GIDA) community. The research aims to profile participants based on age, sex, civil status, income, occupation, living arrangement, and educational attainment. It also evaluates their levels of social isolation, loneliness, and physical health outcomes using the Barthel index. Additionally, the study examines the correlation between these factors and determines whether demographic profiles influence the outcomes. The findings reveal that the majority of participants are aged 60-65, with a slightly higher number of females compared to males. Most have only elementary education and live with a spouse. The study identifies significant feelings of exclusion among the participants, moderate social isolation, and high independence in daily activities. Older age groups, particularly those aged 76-85, experience higher levels of loneliness. A notable but small negative correlation exists between physical health outcomes and social isolation, indicating that increased social isolation may lead to worse physical health outcomes. No significant correlation was found between loneliness and social isolation. Based on these results, the study highlights the critical impact of loneliness on physical health and the need for targeted interventions. The proposed intervention plan includes workshops to enhance social engagement, medical programs to support physical and emotional health, and

emergency preparedness initiatives. The plan emphasizes securing funding, collaborating with health units, organizing outreach and social events, and distributing assistive devices and emergency kits. Ongoing monitoring and evaluation will ensure the effectiveness of the interventions and adjust strategies as needed. This research contributes valuable insights into the social and health challenges faced by senior citizens in GIDA communities and underscores the importance of comprehensive support strategies to improve their quality of life.

Keywords: *GIDA Community, Loneliness, Physical Health, Senior Citizens, and Social Isolation*

INTRODUCTION

Old age is an inevitable and natural phase of life, following youth and middle age, marking the final stage of one's journey. As an integral part of the human lifespan, it is closely associated with the aging process. Senior citizens, having accumulated a wealth of knowledge, experience, and wisdom over the years, undergo significant changes due to aging. These changes increase their vulnerability to illnesses and create a greater need for specific health and social care. Aging affects physical, cognitive, social, and emotional functioning, leading to various challenges in these areas.

In the Philippines, strong familial ties often ensure that many senior citizens live with their adult children, where they receive respect, power, and influence. However, changes in family structures can impact the well-being of seniors. Their living arrangements are crucial predictors of their health status and their use of healthcare services. Living in isolated or impoverished neighborhoods is particularly challenging for seniors, as social isolation and a lack of support pose significant health risks. This isolation has a profound effect on their health and their use of healthcare services.

Aging-related issues such as loss of relationships, medical conditions, and declining functionality make social isolation and loneliness especially relevant to the physical, mental, and long-term health of seniors (Donovan & Blazer, 2020). In various adult subgroups, the prevalence of social isolation or loneliness is influenced by demographic factors such as socioeconomic status, race and ethnicity, gender, education, employment, and marital status. Research shows that individuals who report feeling lonely are more likely to have low income and assets, poor physical and mental health, and are often unmarried (Kearns et al., 2015).

Although the terms loneliness and social isolation are often used interchangeably, they are distinct and must be examined together when analyzing their health implications (Malcolm, Frost & Cowie, 2019). Not all socially isolated individuals experience loneliness, and loneliness can exist even in the absence of social isolation. Loneliness is defined as the perceived gap between the actual and desired quality or quantity of relationships, while social isolation refers to an objectively measurable deficiency in an

individual's social connections, often assessed by the size, diversity, or frequency of interactions in their social network (McLay et al., 2021).

Research by Hoogendijk et al. (2020) indicates that seniors who experience loneliness or social isolation are at a higher risk of death. Prolonged loneliness can lead to serious physiological issues and contribute to motor decline in old age (Asghar & Iqbal, 2019).

The proportion of senior citizens is increasing in many countries, including the Philippines, as demographic shifts create new challenges and demands. According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), the number of Filipinos aged 60 and older reached 9.22 million in 2020, doubling the 4.6 million seniors recorded in 2000. However, most studies in the Philippines have focused on seniors' perceptions, quality of life, and participation in the labor force (Moncatar et al., 2021). Few studies have examined social isolation, loneliness, and physical health outcomes among seniors, especially in Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Areas (GIDAs).

GIDAs are communities that are geographically and economically isolated from mainstream society, characterized by physical challenges such as distance, difficult terrain, and transportation issues, as well as socioeconomic factors like high poverty rates and vulnerable populations. These areas often suffer from inadequate health facilities and services, leading to visible health disparities compared to urban settings (Collado, 2019).

In Bohol, 64 barangays across 20 municipalities are classified as GIDAs (DOH, 2023). Among them, the municipality of Batuan has the lowest population and income-weighted average, ranking as a 5th-class municipality. Two barangays in Batuan, Aloja and Behind the Clouds, are part of the GIDA community, with 95 and 33 senior citizens, respectively. The researchers chose Barangay Aloja for this study due to its significant number of senior citizens and the need for a sufficient sample size. Aloja, being a GIDA, faces physical and socioeconomic challenges, including limited access to healthcare and the impact of armed conflict. These disparities in healthcare services and access, compared to urban settings, should be a concern for policymakers, as they directly affect health outcomes (Collado, 2019).

Despite their differences, social isolation and loneliness are interconnected and can significantly impact the quality of life of senior citizens (Donovan & Blazer, 2020). However, research on these issues in the Philippines is limited, particularly in disadvantaged areas like GIDAs.

Given the anticipated growth of the senior population, this study focuses on recent findings regarding social isolation, loneliness, and physical health outcomes among senior citizens in the GIDA community. The researchers aim to determine the extent of social isolation and loneliness among seniors in GIDA, considering their demographic profiles and different physical health outcomes.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine social isolation, loneliness, and physical health outcomes among senior citizens living in a GIDA community. Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the participants in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Sex;
 - 1.3 Civil Status;
 - 1.4 Income and Source of Income;
 - 1.5 Occupation;
 - 1.6 Living Arrangement; and
 - 1.7 Educational Attainment?
2. What is the participant's degree of social isolation in terms of:
 - 2.1 social participation and engagement
 - 2.2 composition of social network;
 - 2.3 number of close social relationships;
 - 2.4 contact with the social network; and
 - 2.5. perceived social support (relationship quality)?
3. What is the degree of loneliness among senior citizens living in the GIDA community?
4. What is the participant's physical health outcome utilizing the Barthel index among senior citizens living in a GIDA community?
5. Is there a significant difference in participants' social isolation, loneliness, and physical health outcomes among senior citizens living in a GIDA community when grouped according to their demographic profile?
6. Is there a significant relationship between social isolation, and loneliness to physical health outcomes?
7. Based on the findings of the study what proposed intervention plan can be implemented?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive quantitative research design, utilizing an adapted and modified questionnaire from UCLA to assess the level of loneliness among senior citizens. A descriptive quantitative approach is particularly suitable for this study's objectives, allowing for the generalization of findings to the broader senior citizen population in GIDA. By using this design, the researchers can stratify the data by demographic variables, enabling a deeper understanding of variations within the population. The descriptive quantitative research design facilitated the collection of data from a representative sample, providing a comprehensive view of social isolation and loneliness among senior citizens in the GIDA community. The numerical results obtained were instrumental in achieving the study's aim of understanding the current situation and physical health outcomes within this population. Additionally, the data collected serve as a baseline for future comparisons and interventions.

Research Environment

The researchers selected Barangay Aloja in the municipality of Batuan, Bohol, as the setting for this study because it is designated as one of the Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Areas (GIDA) in the province. The decision to choose this location was guided by the DOH-Administrative Order No. 2020-0023, which outlines the criteria for identifying GIDA and strengthening their health systems. Among the 64 barangays across 20 municipalities in Bohol identified as GIDA (DOH, 2023), Batuan stands out as the municipality with the lowest overall percentage, amounting to 0.010, and a provincial score of 0.2619, classifying it as a 5th-class municipality according to the Department of Trade and Industry (2022). This low population and income-weighted average meet the criteria for both physical and socioeconomic disadvantages. Within Batuan, two barangays—Aloja and Behind the Clouds—are part of the GIDA community. Barangay Aloja was specifically chosen for the study because it has a significantly larger population of senior citizens, with 95 residents compared to 33 in Behind the Clouds, making it a more suitable location for gathering the necessary data.

Research Participants

Purposive sampling was meticulously applied in this study to select research participants who meet specific predefined criteria, ensuring alignment with the study's objectives. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were clearly established to enhance the study's coherence and validity. The inclusion criteria required participants to be senior individuals aged 60 years and above, with intact mental cognition, full consciousness, and coherence. This group included those with or without chronic health issues, provided they had given informed consent. The study specifically focused on seniors residing in a Geographically Isolated and Disadvantaged Area (GIDA), emphasizing the relevance of the contextual setting. The exclusion criteria eliminated individuals under the age of 60, as they did not meet the senior age requirement. Those lacking mental competence were also excluded to ensure coherent and reliable responses. Additionally, participants who initially consented but later withdrew from the study were excluded to maintain the integrity of the data. Finally, temporary residents of Aloja, Batuan, Bohol were excluded to ensure consistency in the participant demographic.

Research Instrument

The researchers used an adapted and standardized questionnaire to gather data, employing three primary instruments. First, a 4-item Loneliness Scale adapted from the UCLA Loneliness Scale assessed the emotional state of loneliness among seniors, with responses rated on a 4-point scale ranging from "Hardly Ever" to "Always." Second, indicators of social isolation were measured using two questionnaires from the Health and Retirement Study. The Level of Participation and Social Engagement, a 20-item questionnaire evaluating the frequency of participation in various activities, and a series of questions assessing social network, integration, and relationship quality. Lastly, the Barthel Index was adapted to measure seniors' ability to perform daily activities, providing

quantitative data on their functional independence. These instruments offered a comprehensive view of loneliness, social isolation, and physical health among senior citizens in the GIDA community, guiding targeted interventions.

Data Gathering Procedure

Data gathering commenced after securing all necessary permissions from the university and the local authorities. Researchers obtained approval from the Barangay Captain and the Senior Citizen group's President in Aloja, Batuan. Participants were informed before their assembly to allow ample decision-making time. Questionnaires were distributed following a monthly assembly at the barangay activity center, with house-to-house interviews conducted for those unable to attend. Data collection occurred in September 2023, after which responses were sorted, tabulated, and interpreted.

Data Analysis

Statistical Treatment. The data was subjected to statistical treatment for analysis and interpretation.

1. Identified the profile of the participants in terms of age, sex; civil status; income; occupation; living arrangement; and educational attainment, the percentage formula was used:

$$\% = \frac{f}{N} * 100$$

Where: % = percent
 f = frequency
 N = number of cases

2. Identified the participant's level of social isolation and the level of loneliness, the weighted mean formula was used:

$$\bar{x} = \frac{\sum fx}{N}$$

where : $\sum fx$ – the sum of the products of frequencies and their weight
 N - the number of respondents

The computed weighted mean was interpreted for the degree of loneliness using the following scale:

Weighted Scale	Numerical Value	Description
4	3.4 – 4.0	Always/ High Degree
3	2.6 – 3.3	Sometimes/ Moderate Degree
2	1.8 – 2.5	Rarely/ Low Degree
1	1.0 – 1.7	Never / Very Low Degree

N- the number of respondents

The computed weighted mean was interpreted for the degree of social isolation using the following scale:

Weighted Scale	Numerical Value	Description
5	4.21 – 5.0	Never/Not Relevant
4	3.41 – 4.2	At least once a month
3	2.61– 3.4	Once a week
2	1.82 – 2.6	Several Times a week

3. Identified the participant's physical health outcome in living in a GIDA community the rank formula was used.

4. Identified the significant difference between social isolation, loneliness, and physical health outcomes among senior citizens living in a GIDA community when grouped according to their demographic profile, the one-way ANOVA was used:

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares (MS)	F
Within	$SSW = \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{i=1}^t (X - \bar{X})^2$	$df_w = k - 1$	$MSW = \frac{SSW}{df_w}$	$F = \frac{MSB}{MSW}$
Between	$SSB = \sum_{j=1}^k (\bar{X}_j - \bar{X})^2$	$df_b = n - k$	$MSB = \frac{SSB}{df_b}$	
Total	$SST = \sum_{j=1}^n (\bar{X}_j - \bar{X})^2$	$df_t = n - 1$		

5. Identified the significant relationship between social isolation, loneliness to physical health outcomes, the Pearson correlation was used using the formula:

$$r = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{\sqrt{[n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2 - n(\sum y^2) - (\sum y)^2]}}$$

Where:

- n = number of pairs of scores
- $\sum xy$ = sum of the product of paired scores
- $\sum x$ = sum of the x scores
- $\sum y$ = sum of the y scores
- $\sum x^2$ = sum of the squares of the x scores
- $\sum y^2$ = sum of the squares of the y scores

RESULTS

Table 1. Age and Sex, Civil Status, Educational Attainment Crosstabulation

Educational attainment		Sex	Civil status				Total
			single	married	widowed	separated	
Elementary	60-65	F	1	5	1		7
		M	1	3		1	5
	66-70	F		8			8
		M	1	2			3
	71-75	F		4			4
		M	1	3			4
	76-80	F		2	2		4
		M		3	1		4

		81-85	F			1		1
			M		1			1
Elementary Graduate	age	60-65	F		1			1
		66-70	M		1			1
		71-80	F			1		1
		81-85	M		1			1
No formal Education	age	71-75	M		1			1
		76-80	F		1			1
		81-85	M		2			2
		86-90	F			1		1
	Total				4	38	7	1

Table 1 shows the crosstabulation of age, sex, civil status, and educational attainment among senior citizens. Out of 50 participants, 41 are elementary graduates, with the majority being married, and fewer are single, widowed, or separated. Among the elementary graduates, there are 24 females and 17 males. Four of these graduates are between 60 and 85 years old, including two males and two females.

Only five individuals have no formal education, with the highest number in the 81-85 age range. This group includes three males and two females, most of whom are married, with one widowed.

The data shows a slight gender imbalance with more females than males. Most seniors are married, reflecting a preference for companionship, while the notable number of widowed seniors indicates the loss of spouses. The lack of separated individuals suggests cohabitation may be rare or underreported. Most seniors have only completed elementary education, likely due to poverty and limited access to further education.

According to the Philippine Statistics Authority (2022), the sex ratio for those aged 65 and over is 73 males per 100 females, indicating higher female life expectancy or higher male mortality in older age groups. In 2020, seniors comprised 8.5% of the population, up from 7.5% in 2015, with a consistent higher proportion of females. Kislev (2022) found that married elders experience less loneliness compared to those who are single, widowed, or divorced. Loneliness in old age is often linked to declining health and the challenges of managing issues alone.

**Table 2. Occupation, Income, and Source of Income Crosstabulation
N=50**

Occupation			Source of income					Total	
			work	pension	vendor	farming	Income of child		others
employed	income	5k below	2	2		3	0	1	8
		6-10K	0	0		0	1	0	1
		6-10k	0	0		0	1	0	1
	Total		2	2		3	2	1	10
unemployed	income	5k below	0	1	6	4	3		14
		5k-low	1	5	0	10	5		21
		6-10K	0	0	0	0	1		1
		6-10k	0	0	0	0	2		2
		6k-10	0	0	0	0	2		2
	Total		1	6	6	14	13		40

Table 2 provides insights into the occupational status, income levels, and sources of income among senior citizens. The data shows that most senior citizens who are employed earn less than P5,000 per month, with two earning between P6,000 and P10,000. There is also a senior citizen who earns income through farming. Notably, no unemployed senior citizens appear to receive income from pensions, vending, or other sources listed in the table.

In contrast, unemployed senior citizens show a more diverse range of income sources. The majority of unemployed seniors earn less than P5,000 per month, with the largest group (14 individuals) earning from various sources, including pensions, vending, farming, and income from their children. The data indicates that unemployed seniors rely on multiple sources of income to meet their needs, highlighting the economic challenges faced by this group.

This distribution illustrates that many senior citizens remain actively engaged in the workforce, likely due to economic necessity, the need for ongoing income, or a desire to stay active. However, the presence of jobless seniors underscores the difficulties this demographic may encounter, such as retirement, health issues, or challenges in re-entering the workforce.

Senior citizens are often the most vulnerable demographic in the job market due to physical and functional health risks, ageism, and psychological factors like work stress (Malik et al., 2022). Despite this, many seniors continue to work because their pensions and retirement savings are insufficient to sustain their families and needs. This reality aligns with reports from the Commission on Human Rights (2020) indicating that poverty is a significant challenge for senior Filipinos, with around 9.1% of senior citizens classified as poor (PSA, 2020). Many senior citizens continue to work informally out of necessity, with 7% of adults aged 80 and above relying on income from unpaid labor.

**Table 3. Living Arrangement
N=50**

Living Arrangement	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Living Alone	15	30
Living with a partner	22	44
Living with children and grandchildren	12	24
Living with relatives	1	2
Total	50	100

Table 3 indicates that the most common living arrangement among the 50 senior citizens is living with a partner, accounting for 44% of the participants. Living alone is the next most common arrangement at 30%, followed by living with children and grandchildren at 24%. Only 2% of participants live with other relatives.

These findings highlight the importance of shared housing and companionship for seniors, with many choosing to live with their spouses. The significant number of seniors living alone suggests a mix of personal choice and necessity. The presence of multigenerational households reflects the cultural emphasis on familial support and intergenerational cohabitation.

In line with national and international research, cohabitation with a partner is linked to better physical and mental health in seniors, as it fosters mutual support and reduces social isolation (Bolina et al., 2021). The prevalence of multigenerational living arrangements also underscores the reliance of seniors on family, particularly children, for care and support, a common practice in the Philippines and abroad (Medina & Medina, 2023).

**Table 4. Degree of Loneliness
N=50**

Degree of Loneliness	Weighted Mean	Description
1. How often do you feel that you lack companionship? (2)	2.48	Rarely/Low Degree

2. How often do you feel alone? ((4)	2.68	Sometimes/Moderate Degree
3. How often do you feel that you are no longer close to anyone? (7)	2.04	Rarely/Low Degree
4. How often do you feel like you have nowhere to turn? (3)	1.96	Rarely/Low Degree
5. How often do you feel close to people? (10)	3.12	Sometimes/Moderate Degree
6. How often do you feel isolated from others? (14)	2.48	Rarely/Low Degree
7. How often do you feel left out? (11)	3.26	Always/High Degree
8. How often do you feel that no one knows you well?	2.24	Rarely/Low Degree
9. How often do you feel shy?	2.52	Sometimes/Moderate Degree
10. How often do you feel that your relationships with others are not meaningful?	2.34	Rarely/Low Degree
<i>Composite Mean</i>	<i>2.51</i>	<i>Sometimes/Moderate Degree</i>

Legend: 1.0-1.7 Never/Very Low Degree, 1.8-2.5 Rarely/Low Degree, 2.6-3.3 Sometimes/Moderate Degree, 3.4-4.1 Always/High Degree

Table 4 presents data on the loneliness levels among senior citizens, revealing that feelings of exclusion are the most frequently experienced, with a weighted mean of 3.26. This aligns with the findings of Huxhold, Suanet, and Wetzel (2022), who emphasize social exclusion as a primary component of loneliness due to deficient social networks. A sense of closeness to others, which respondents sometimes felt, follows with a weighted mean of 3.12, supporting Okyere et al. (2021), who underscore the role of social connectedness in reducing loneliness. Occasional loneliness and shyness were also noted, with weighted means of 2.68 and 2.52, respectively. Less frequently reported were feelings of loneliness and lack of company, both with a weighted mean of 2.48, as well as a sense of meaningless connections and not being well-known to others, with means of 2.34 and 2.24. The least reported feelings were a lack of closeness to others and having no one to turn to, with weighted means of 2.04 and 1.96. Overall, the composite mean of 2.51 indicates that respondents experienced moderate levels of loneliness, with social exclusion and connectedness being the most prominent features. These findings resonate with Tomassini et al. (2020), who highlight the higher incidence of loneliness in deprived rural areas, independent of individual factors.

Table 5. Extent of Social Isolation

Extent of Social Isolation	Composite Mean	Description
Social Participation and Engagement	3.60	At least once a month
Number of close relationships	1.80	Close
Contact with Social Network	4.31	Once or twice a month
Perceived Social Support	2.63	A little

Table 5 presents the extent of social isolation among senior citizens across various factors. The composite mean of 3.60 indicates that senior citizens participate in social events at least once a month, showing moderate social engagement. Despite this, the number of close relationships is low, with a mean of 1.80, suggesting that intimate connections are limited. However, social network contact is relatively frequent, with a mean of 4.31, indicating that most engage with their social networks once or twice a month. Perceived social support is moderate, with a mean of 2.63.

Key insights include that senior citizens in Aloja Batuan participate in physical activities such as walking and gardening weekly and engage in hobbies and personal projects regularly, indicating a focus on personal growth and family ties. However, there is less participation in social activities like volunteering, which suggests a need for increased opportunities for community engagement to enhance their quality of life.

Research supports the importance of social engagement for senior citizens' well-being, including mental health and cognitive function (Siette et al., 2020). The findings emphasize the need for initiatives that encourage more frequent physical activity and social interaction, particularly through digital platforms that have become vital for maintaining social connections. Despite moderate levels of perceived social support, efforts should be made to improve the depth of social relationships and community participation among senior citizens in Aloja Batuan.

**Table 6. Composition of Social Network
N=50**

Table 6 highlights the composition of social networks among senior citizens, revealing that most have strong social ties. All 50 participants reported having friends, emphasizing the importance of social interaction and support outside of immediate family. Regarding direct family members—such as parents, siblings, and cousins—43 participants confirmed their presence, while 7 did not. Similarly, 40 participants reported having living children, whereas 10 did not. The data was more evenly split concerning having a spouse, husband, wife, or partner, with 32 participants acknowledging such a relationship and 18 indicating otherwise.

These findings underscore the diversity of social networks among senior citizens, with strong friendships being a common thread. While most participants maintain close family relationships, there is variability in family structures, particularly concerning the presence of children and partners. This complexity in social ties reflects the different ways senior citizens maintain their social welfare and support systems.

The results align with existing research on the importance of social connections in later life, highlighting those strong social ties, especially friendships, are crucial to the well-being of senior citizens (Bruine, Parker, & Strough, 2020).

**Table 7. Physical Health Outcomes
N=50**

Barthel Index of Activities of Daily Living	Mode	Interpretation
1. Bathing	2	<i>Independent (in water dipper)</i>
2. Dressing	3	Independent (including buttons, zips, laces & etc.)
3. Toileting	3	Independent (on, off, wiping)

4. Transferring	4	independent
5. Feeding	3	Independent (food provided within reach)
6. Grooming	2	Independent (face, hair, teeth, shaving) implements provided
7. Mobility	3	Independent (but may use any aid, e.g. stick)
8. Stairs or Steps	3	Independent (up or down)
9. Bowel	3	continent
10. Bladder	3	Continent (for over 7 days)

Table 7 presents data on the physical health outcomes of senior citizens in a GIDA community, as measured by the Barthel Index of Activities of Daily Living. The table includes activities such as bathing, dressing, toileting, transferring, feeding, grooming, mobility, navigating stairs, and continence. The mode score for each activity, representing the most frequent response, indicates the level of independence among participants.

The data reveals a high degree of independence across various daily tasks. For instance, most seniors are able to bathe and dress independently, with mode scores of 2 and 3, respectively, indicating they can manage tasks like buttoning and lacing on their own. Similarly, the mode scores of 3 for toileting and 4 for transferring show that most participants can perform these activities without assistance. In terms of mobility, a mode score of 3 for stairs and steps indicates that many seniors can navigate them independently, often using aids like walking sticks. Additionally, the mode scores of 3 for both bowel and bladder control suggest that most seniors maintain continence.

However, the distribution of scores reveals some variation in functional abilities. While 16 out of 50 seniors achieved a perfect score of 20, indicating full independence in all activities, 34 seniors scored below 20, suggesting that a significant portion of the population may require some assistance. Notably, 5 seniors scored below 15, indicating a higher need for help with daily tasks.

These findings underscore the overall high level of independence among seniors in the community but also highlight the importance of recognizing individual differences in functional abilities. Addressing these needs can help improve the well-being and quality of life for all seniors in the community.

Table 8. Social isolation, loneliness, and physical health outcomes among senior citizens when grouped according to their demographic profiles.

N= 50

Variables		Age	Civil Status	Income	Sex	Source of Income	Living Arrangement	Educational Attainment
Loneliness	Mean	60-65yrs.: 2.58 66-70yrs.: 2.19 71-75yrs.:2.62 76-80yrs.: 2.73 81-85yrs. 1.90	Single:2.88 Widowed: 2.77 Married:2.37 Separated: 2.65	5k low: 2.69 6-10K: 2.64	Female: 2.49 Male: 2.39	Pension: 2.65 Vendor:2.52 Farmer:2.23 Salary: 2.44 Support from children & Grandchildren: 2.89	Living alone: 2.26 Living with partner: 2.55 Living with children & GC: 2.43 Living with relatives: 2.42	No formal education: 2.5 Elem. Grad.:2.52 Elem level: 2.49
	Computed F-value	2.819	0.17	0.24	-0.03	1.34	0.33	-0.17
	P-value	0.03	0.95	0.81	0.97	0.27	0.81	0.98
	Decision on Ho	Reject Ho	Accept Ho	Accept Ho	Accept Ho	Accept Ho	Accept Ho	Accept ho
	Interpretation	Significant	Not significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant
Social Isolation	Mean	60-65yrs.: 3.27 66-70yrs.: 3.12 71-75yrs.:3.37 76-80yrs.: 3.39 81-85yrs. 3.41	Single:3.21 Widowed: 3.29 Married:3.05 Separated: 2.81	5k low: 3.2 6-10K: 2.94	Female: 3.16 Male: 3.05	Pension: 3.04 Vendor:3.07 Farmer:2.92 Salary: 3.16 Support from children & Grandchildren: 3.28	Living alone: 2.85 Living with partner: 3.01 Living with children & GC: 2.13 Living with relatives: 2.99	No formal education: 3.33 Elem. Grad.:2.75 Elem level: 3.12
	Computed F-value	0.24	0.95	0.65	0.34	0.36	0.33	1.79
	P-value	0.92	0.42	0.52	0.73	0.84	0.81	0.17
	Decision on Ho	Accept Ho	Accept Ho	Accept Ho	Accept Ho	Accept Ho	Accept Ho	Accept Ho
	Interpretation	No Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant	Not Significant
Physical Health Outcome	Mean	60-65yrs.: 1.85 66-70yrs.: 1.92 71-75yrs.:1.85 76-80yrs.: 1.80 81-85yrs. 1.70	Single:1.74 Widowed: 1.84 Married:1.83 Separated: 1.95	5k low: 1.83 6-10K: 1.87	Female: 1.86 Male: 1.79	Pension: 1.80 Vendor:2.0 Farmer:1.95 Salary: 2.06 Support from children & Grandchildren: 1.89	Living alone: 1.85 Living with partner: 1.58 Living with children & GC: 1.15 Living with relatives: 1.88	No formal education: 1.64 Elem. Grad.:1.88 Elem level: 1.85

Table 8 analyzed the differences in social isolation, loneliness, and physical health outcomes among senior citizens in a GIDA community, considering demographic factors such as age, sex, civil status, income and source of income, occupation, living arrangement, and educational attainment. The analysis, using F-values and p-values, revealed various trends within these demographic groups.

A significant difference in loneliness was found among different age groups, with a calculated F-value of 2.819 and a p-value of 0.03, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis (Ho). However, no significant differences were observed in social isolation and physical health outcomes when comparing age groups ($F = 0.24$, $p = 0.92$). The acceptance of Ho in these cases indicates that social isolation levels and physical health outcomes do not vary significantly across different age cohorts.

The study found that senior citizens aged 76-85 reported higher levels of loneliness compared to younger age groups, suggesting that age-related factors may influence how loneliness impacts physical health among seniors in this community. This highlights the importance of considering age when addressing social and health issues in aging populations. Other demographic factors did not show a significant effect on the relationship between physical health outcomes, loneliness, and social isolation.

The findings align with previous research by Schutter et al. (2022), which indicates that loneliness increases with age due to factors like changing social networks, the loss of loved ones, and reduced mobility. The study also emphasizes the importance of social connections for mental and physical health, especially as individuals age, and recognizes that while physical, sensory, and cognitive functions may decline, social functioning remains adaptable and responsive to intervention (Van Orden et al., 2021).

Overall, the study suggests that loneliness and social isolation may have different effects on health outcomes. Loneliness may have more immediate physiological impacts, potentially affecting immune and neuroendocrine responses, while social isolation may contribute indirectly to unmet care needs and poorer health outcomes.

Table 9. Social isolation, loneliness, to physical health outcomes among senior citizens living in a GIDA community.

N= 50

Variables	Computed Pearson R-value	P-value	Decision on Ho	Interpretation
Loneliness & social isolation	0.11	0.089	Accept Ho	Not Significant, Weak relationship
Loneliness & physical health outcomes	0.08	0.32	Accept Ho	Not Significant, No relationship
Social isolation & physical health outcomes	-0.35	0.03	Reject Ho	Significant, Small negative relationship

Table 9 examines the relationships between social isolation, loneliness, and physical health outcomes among 50 senior citizens living in a GIDA community. The analysis used Pearson correlation coefficients and corresponding p-values to assess these relationships. The findings show that the correlation between loneliness and social isolation (Pearson R-value = 0.11, p-value = 0.089) is weak and statistically insignificant. Similarly, the relationship between loneliness and physical health outcomes (Pearson R-value = 0.08, p-value = 0.32) is also insignificant, indicating no direct impact of loneliness on physical health. In contrast, the relationship between social isolation and physical health outcomes (Pearson R-value = -0.35, p-value = 0.03) is significant, revealing a small negative correlation. This suggests that higher levels of social isolation are associated with slightly worse physical health outcomes among the senior citizens.

These results highlight that, although loneliness and social isolation do not significantly impact each other or physical health directly, social isolation is associated with poorer physical health. This finding is consistent with research by Naito et al. (2021), which identified a stronger association between social isolation and disability in rural areas compared to urban settings, reinforcing the complex relationship between social isolation and health. The study emphasizes the importance of addressing social isolation as a potential risk factor for declining health among seniors, even though loneliness itself may not directly affect physical health outcomes.

DISCUSSION

Findings

Considering the results of the statistical analysis, the following findings were obtained:

1. The study shows a breakdown of the respondents' ages and genders, showing that the most common age group is 60–65, with 66–70, 71–75, 76–80, and 81–85 following in decreasing order of frequency. Interestingly, in the whole sample, there are somewhat more girls than males.
2. When it comes to educational attainment, most of them reached elementary level only. Most senior citizens live with a spouse, according to the research findings.
3. Significant feelings of exclusion were regularly felt by respondents. This implies that people felt excluded a lot.
4. The study showed a moderate degree of social isolation among seniors in Aloja, Batuan, who routinely engaged in a variety of activities, especially family gatherings and solitary hobbies.
5. The respondents demonstrated a high degree of independence in activities such as dressing, bathing, using the restroom, and moving around.
6. Older age groups—that is, those 76–80 and 81–85 years old—tend to report higher degrees of loneliness, indicating that age-related factors are important in determining how loneliness affects seniors' physical health outcomes.
7. It found a small but significant negative correlation between physical health outcomes and social isolation, suggesting that higher levels of social isolation are associated with slightly worse physical health outcomes, even though there was no significant correlation found between loneliness and social isolation.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers therefore concluded that the study provides insights into the social, emotional, and physical health outcomes among senior citizens living in the GIDA community. The study reveals the exact aspect of social isolation, loneliness, and physical health outcomes among senior citizens. The participants' level of loneliness tends to increase with age, social isolation shows minor variations across demographic profiles. There is no significant difference among Social Isolation, Loneliness, and Physical health outcomes among senior citizens living in a GIDA community except for age being a significant factor in the relationship between loneliness and physical health. Above all, the study emphasizes the importance of loneliness, especially to senior citizen individuals, as it appears to have a significant impact on physical health outcomes.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made given the inferences drawn from the study's findings:

1. **Appropriate Budget Allocation.** The barangay officials of Aloja should propose a budget for workshops on crafts, technology, or other hobbies to promote socialization and skill development for senior citizens.

2. Implement medical programs and community resources to improve their well-being while recognizing their level of education and family situation.
3. That the health educators in the RHUs must also think of more effective and relevant programs to address the problems in their area.
4. RHU should organize outreach programs specifically for those areas that are part of GIDA for them to socially engage and participate in different activities
5. That the DOH should donate free assistive devices to senior citizens since most of them are using improvised ambulatory devices.
6. Senior citizen organizations will host a weekly or monthly film screenings, providing opportunities for socialization and reflection on psychosocial health.
7. That the RHU should provide emergency kits for each household in the GIDA community. This is important in isolated areas where emergency services may take longer to respond.

PROPOSED INTERVENTION PLAN IN ENHANCING SENIOR WELL-BEING IN GIDA COMMUNITIES

Rationale

The intervention plan is designed to address critical issues identified among senior citizens in the GIDA community, including social isolation, loneliness, and physical health concerns. Given those older adults, particularly those in remote areas, face significant challenges related to social engagement and access to resources, the proposed plan seeks to mitigate these issues by fostering social connections, enhancing medical support, and improving emergency preparedness. This approach aims to create a more inclusive and supportive environment for seniors, ultimately contributing to their overall well-being and quality of life.

Objectives

- To reduce feelings of exclusion and loneliness among senior citizens through increased social engagement and community activities.
- To enhance the physical and emotional well-being of seniors by implementing targeted medical programs and support services.
- To ensure that senior citizens in GIDA communities are prepared for emergencies with adequate resources and support.

Mechanics of Implementation

To implement the plan, the first step involves securing budget allocation from barangay officials to fund workshops and activities. Collaborations with RHUs will be crucial for developing and delivering medical programs and support services. Outreach programs targeting GIDA areas will be organized to increase social engagement, while the DOH will coordinate the distribution of assistive devices to those in need. Regular film screenings and social events will be hosted by senior citizen organizations to foster community interaction. Emergency kits will be prepared and distributed to households in GIDA areas to ensure preparedness.

Schedule of Implementation

The implementation will commence with securing the necessary budget and planning workshops in the first month. By the second month, medical programs and outreach initiatives will be launched, and assistive devices will be distributed. The third month will see the first film screening and social event, followed by the distribution of emergency kits. Ongoing efforts will focus on maintaining regular events and making adjustments based on feedback and effectiveness.

Monitoring and Evaluation

Monitoring will involve regular check-ins and evaluations to track the progress and effectiveness of each program component. This will be done through surveys, feedback forms, and participation records, with monthly reviews and quarterly assessments. Evaluation will include comparing pre- and post-intervention data, conducting participant interviews, and reviewing outcomes to ensure the programs meet their objectives and make necessary improvements.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Ethical concerns were addressed by obtaining necessary permits and ensuring full transparency. The researchers personally delivered research tools to respondents with administrative support, and informed consent was obtained from participants individually. Names were optional and coded to ensure confidentiality. Data protection included restricted access to records. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any time without penalty.

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